

Published in final edited form as:

J Biomed Mater Res A. 2020 February ; 108(2): 279–291. doi:10.1002/jbm.a.36814.

Tunable Methacrylated Hyaluronic Acid-based Hydrogels as Scaffolds for Soft Tissue Engineering Applications

Benjamin S. Spearman¹, Nikunj K. Agrawal¹, Andrés Rubiano², Chelsey S. Simmons^{1,2}, Sahba Mobini^{1,3,4,*}, Christine E. Schmidt^{1,*}

¹J. Crayton Pruitt Family Department of Biomedical Engineering, University of Florida, Gainesville, FL

²Department of Mechanical & Aerospace Engineering, University of Florida, Gainesville, FL

³Instituto de Micro y Nanotecnología, IMN-CNM, CSIC (CEI UAM+CSIC), Madrid, Spain

⁴Departamento de Biología Molecular and Centro de Biología Molecular, Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, Madrid, Spain

Abstract

Hyaluronic acid (HA)-based biomaterials have been explored for a number of applications in biomedical engineering, particularly as tissue regeneration scaffolds. Crosslinked forms of HA are more robust and provide tunable mechanical properties and degradation rates that are critical in regenerative medicine; however, crosslinking modalities reported in the literature vary and there are few comparisons of different scaffold properties for various crosslinking approaches. In this study we offer direct comparison of two methacrylation techniques for HA (glycidyl methacrylate HA (GMHA) or methacrylic anhydride HA (MAHA)). The two methods for methacrylating HA provide degrees of methacrylation ranging from 2.4% up to 86%, reflecting a wider range of properties than is possible using only a single methacrylation technique. We have also characterized mechanical properties for nine different tissues isolated from rat (ranging from lung at the softest to muscle at the stiffest) using indentation techniques and show that we can match the full range of mechanical properties (0.35 kPa to 6.13 kPa) using either GMHA or MAHA. To illustrate utility for neural tissue engineering applications, functional hydrogels with adhesive proteins (either GMHA or MAHA base hydrogels with collagen I and laminin) were designed with effective moduli mechanically matched to rat sciatic nerve (2.47 ± 0.31 kPa). We demonstrated ability of these hydrogels to support 3D axonal elongation from dorsal root ganglia cultures. Overall, we have shown that methacrylated HA provides a tunable platform with a wide range of properties for use in soft tissue engineering.

Keywords

Hyaluronic acid hydrogels; Hydrogel mechanical characterization; Soft tissue engineering

*Corresponding Author: Christine E. Schmidt, J. Crayton Pruitt Family Department of Biomedical Engineering, P.O. Box 116131, The University of Florida, Gainesville FL 32611-6131, Phone: +1 352-273-9222, schmidt@bme.ufl.edu; Sahba Mobini, Instituto de Micro y Nanotecnología, IMN-CNM, Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas, Calle Isaac Newton 8, 28760 Tres Cantos, Spain, Phone: +34 91-8372226, sahba.mobini@csic.es.

Introduction

In tissue engineering, the condition of the microenvironment in which cells are present is considered essential for regeneration outcomes⁽¹⁾. The biomaterials used in tissue-engineered scaffolds need to be engineered to behave similar to the original tissue or organ in terms of chemical composition, mechanical robustness, and delivering other biological cues. Hydrogels are a compelling type of material for scaffold fabrication because they have similar structure and mechanical properties to that of the extracellular matrix (ECM) of soft tissue^{(2),(3)}. There is a need for inexpensive, effective, and easy-to-use tunable hydrogel platforms for use in soft tissue engineering. Some examples of commonly used platforms in soft tissue engineering include Matrigel (an ECM protein mixture derived from mouse sarcoma cells), collagen-based hydrogels, and polyethylene glycol (PEG). While these platforms work well for some applications, they have limitations. Matrigel is tumor-derived which limits its translatability for human applications⁽⁴⁾. ECM-protein-based scaffolds including collagen and Matrigel lack the easy mechanical and chemical tunability of synthetic platforms such as PEG. For example, collagen and Matrigel-based scaffolds are typically only tunable by changing the concentration of solution or require mixing with additional components. The maximum concentration of these materials is limited by whether they will dissolve in solution, restricting mechanical tunability. Synthetic materials such as PEG, however, do not have the biological advantages of ECM-based materials such as the native role in wound healing and regeneration of hyaluronic acid (HA) and requires modification to induce biological compatibility⁽⁵⁾. Here, we demonstrate that photocrosslinkable methacrylated hyaluronic acid can work as a platform with a wide range of mechanical, biological, and chemical properties for use in both in vitro and in vivo soft tissue engineering.

Among the many natural materials found in the body, HA is a promising candidate for a broad range of biomedical applications such as fabrication of bioengineered scaffolds for cartilage, nerve, and skin tissues in addition to drug delivery systems^{(6),(7)}. HA is a high molecular weight nonsulfated glycosaminoglycan and an ubiquitous ECM component found in nearly all tissues and body fluid in humans^{(8),(9)}. Notable concentrations of HA are present in synovial fluid, the vitreous body of the eye⁽¹⁰⁾, cartilage⁽¹¹⁾, skin, the nervous system⁽¹²⁾, and other tissues^{(13),(14)}. HA acts as a lubricant and shock absorber in joints because of its presence in synovial fluid by increasing the viscosity of the fluid, which reduces friction between joints⁽¹⁴⁾. In skin, HA acts as a scavenger of free radicals generated by UV from the sun, preventing further damage⁽¹⁴⁾. Native HA molecules present in the ECM support tissue organization and regulate angiogenesis⁽¹⁵⁾ and also play a critical role in regeneration and wound healing, particularly in nerve regeneration⁽⁵⁾. In a previously published study, HA-based hydrogels modified with poly-L-lysine (PLL) and nogo-66 receptor antibody (antiNgR) were able to promote in vitro neuronal adhesion and neurite regeneration⁽¹⁶⁾. Other studies have shown that HA helps in reducing the formation of glial scar (barrier for nerve regeneration) after spinal cord injury thereby promoting neurite outgrowth⁽¹⁷⁾. HA-based scaffolds have been shown to aid peripheral nerve regeneration by aiding with the organization of a fibrin network which provides a guided path for axonal regeneration^{(5),(18)}. During regeneration, HA and other glycosaminoglycans form a

hydrogel network that supports cell migration and differentiation. Moreover, studies have shown that HA is anti-inflammatory and non-immunogenic⁽¹⁹⁾ and therefore has been widely studied as a biomaterial platform that offers great potential for both in vitro and in vivo tissue engineering applications^{(20),(21)}.

Besides its biological properties, HA also has a useful chemical structure that makes it an attractive biomaterial. The presence of a variety of functional groups such as carboxyl, hydroxyl, and amide groups on HA's backbone allows for easy modification^{(20),(22),(23)}. Addition of glycidyl methacrylate or methacrylic anhydride to form glycidyl methacrylate HA (GMHA) or methacrylic anhydride HA (MAHA), respectively, result in a UV photocrosslinkable hydrogel^{(24),(25)} which allows for controlled crosslinking resulting in the fabrication of hydrogels resembling native ECM properties. Additionally, cells can be encapsulated in a pre-gel solution which allows for studying their behavior in a 3D microenvironment⁽²⁶⁾. Burdick, et al. used a MAHA-based hydrogel with varying molecular weights of HA to modulate degradation times from less than one day to 38 days in the presence of hyaluronidase. They cultured auricular swine chondrocytes in these photocrosslinked hydrogels, which produced neocartilage in vitro⁽²⁷⁾.

Although HA hydrogels successfully mimic a major component of ECM, HA does not have native peptide moieties associated with adhesion like many ECM proteins do, meaning it often must be combined with adhesive ECM components to provide a proper environment to support cell attachment. For instance, in nerve tissue engineering, HA has been combined with adhesive molecules and critical components of the nerve microenvironment and nerve regenerative signaling pathways such as collagen I, laminin, or fibronectin to support neural cells^{(28),(29)}.

As mentioned above, mechanical properties play a critical role in the regenerative capacity of tissue-engineered scaffolds. For example, dorsal root ganglia (DRG) neurite growth can be limited by agarose gels with increased modulus^{(30),(31)}. In addition, processes critical to regeneration such as cell motility and adhesion have been found to be regulated by substrate stiffness⁽³²⁾.

There are many different techniques for measuring the mechanical properties of hydrogels including compression, rheology, and indentation⁽³³⁾. Compression has substantial constraints for soft hydrogels including bulging of the hydrogel, significant "snap-in" or adhesiveness when plates come into contact with the sample, and inappropriate load cells in traditional mechanical testing machines. Rheology is also commonly used to characterize hydrogels during gelation. This technique can provide storage and loss modulus values at different frequencies of strain, which can be interpreted as viscoelastic properties^{(34),(35)}. However, biological tissue cannot be easily shaped to standard geometries used in rheometers nor characterized during "gelation" stages; therefore, using rheology to match mechanical properties of a hydrogel with native tissue can be misleading. Some have used atomic force microscopy (AFM) to indent HA-based hydrogels⁽²⁵⁾. AFM measures nanoscale properties, which can be useful for measuring homogenous hydrogels, but will not capture the bulk properties because the probe is measuring hyperlocal properties which change based on local cell presence and ECM⁽³⁶⁾.

Finally, millimeter-scale indentation works by depressing the surface of a hydrogel using a rigid probe and measuring the reaction force required to reach a predetermined displacement depth⁽³⁷⁾. Different contact and constitutive models can be applied to obtain viscoelastic properties from force-displacement data, and sample geometries do not restrict the use of indentation as a characterization method, which makes it an ideal technique to compare synthetic hydrogels and biological tissue samples. Here, we demonstrate the range of mechanical and biological properties of hydrogels that are obtainable via the use of methacrylated HA as a platform for soft tissue engineering. In addition, we compare the mechanical properties of these hydrogels to a wide range of soft tissues sourced from rats.

This article provides a perspective on the various techniques used to methacrylate hyaluronic acid (HA) and a comparison of the hydrogel mechanics relative to soft tissues. Although these materials have previously been characterized and published, there have been no direct side-by-side comparison of the methacrylation techniques. These hydrogels were also mechanically characterized using an indentation technique that is particularly well-suited for direct comparisons of the hydrogels with target soft tissues. Methacrylated HA hydrogels had not previously been characterized using this technique. This side-by-side comparison of different methacrylated HA with soft tissues can serve as a centralized resource for researchers in this field, particularly those interested in using methacrylated HA for soft tissue engineering purposes.

We believe having clear knowledge of fabrication techniques and chemical and mechanical properties of HA-based hydrogels is necessary to help tissue engineers choose the relevant scaffold material for their target tissue and application. Therefore, in this study, we describe fabrication methods of HA-based hydrogels for soft tissue engineering and compare chemical, mechanical, and biological properties of these hydrogels. We describe two different techniques for methacrylation of HA which allows both for photocrosslinking of HA (MAHA and GMHA) and tuning of mechanical properties using different concentrations or degrees of methacrylation. These hydrogels have many potential tissue engineering applications, especially when combined with other ECM components. Multi-component hydrogels were developed with the addition of collagen type I and laminin to improve biological properties. These hydrogels were compared chemically (HNMR), mechanically (indentation), and biologically (in vitro tests with Schwann cells and DRGs).

Materials and Method

Materials

Unless noted otherwise, materials were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO). Materials used in this study include hyaluronic acid, acetone (Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA), triethylamine, phosphate buffered saline (PBS), methacrylic anhydride, sodium hydroxide, rat tail collagen I (Fisher Scientific), acetic acid, Cultrex 3D Culture Matrix Laminin I (Trevigen, Gaithersburg, MD), 10X DMEM low glucose, HyClone AdvanceSTEM ES qualified HEPES buffer (Fisher Scientific), and sodium bicarbonate (Avantor, Center Valley, PA).

Hydrogel synthesis

Methacrylation of HA

Glycidyl Methacrylate Hyaluronic Acid (GMHA): To synthesize GMHA, HA was dissolved in a 50% 1X PBS 50% acetone solution at 10 mg/mL. Triethylamine was added and stirred for 30 minutes according to the relevant stoichiometric ratio. Glycidyl methacrylate was then added and stirred overnight. The stoichiometric ratio of glycidyl methacrylate added to each HA monomer was 5X, 10X, or 20X. GMHA solution was precipitated by pouring 50 mL of dissolved solution into 1000 mL of acetone and stirring with a glass rod to collect the precipitate. Once the solution precipitated, GMHA was rinsed with fresh acetone and dissolved in PBS overnight followed by precipitation in acetone again. GMHA solution was then dialyzed against PBS for 3 days with PBS replaced daily. On the third day, the solution was dialyzed against dI water to remove any residual salt from PBS. GMHA solution was sterile filtered, flash frozen, and lyophilized for long-term storage.

Methacrylic Anhydride Hyaluronic Acid (MAHA): To synthesize MAHA, HA was dissolved in dI water at 10 mg/mL. The solution was kept on ice and continuously stirred until all of the methacrylic anhydride was added. Stepwise, methacrylic anhydride was added to the solution based on the appropriate stoichiometric ratio while ensuring the pH remains between 8 and 11 by using 5M NaOH. The stoichiometric ratio of methacrylic anhydride added to each HA monomer was 5X, 10X, 20X, or 40X. After the methacrylic anhydride was completely added, the pH was adjusted to ~9. MAHA solution was precipitated by pouring dissolved solution into 1000 mL of ethanol per 50 mL of solution. Once the solution precipitated, MAHA was rinsed with fresh ethanol and dissolved in dI water overnight followed by precipitation in ethanol again. MAHA was then dialyzed against dI water for 3 days with water replaced daily. MAHA solution was sterile filtered, flash frozen, and lyophilized for long-term storage.

Collagen I—Collagen I was used either as a control for comparison to HA hydrogels or was mixed with HA components to form a multi-component ECM-based hydrogel. Collagen I was received sterile and kept under sterile conditions. Collagen I was prepared by mixing collagen I, 5X DMEM/HEPES, and 0.2% acetic acid at appropriate volumes to reach the desired concentration. 5X DMEM/HEPES is a 1:1 mixture of 10X DMEM low glucose and HyClone AdvanceSTEM HEPES buffer with 23.125 mg of sodium bicarbonate per mL solution. Later, this collagen solution will be mixed with other components if used in multi-component hydrogels.

Multi-Component Hydrogels—To mimic peripheral nerve ECM, multi-component hydrogels containing collagen I, laminin, and/or GMHA or MAHA were made by mixing these components at appropriate concentrations. As noted above, GMHA and MAHA were sterilized prior to lyophilization and were handled under sterile conditions from that point forward. Collagen I and laminin were received sterile. The chemical crosslinker Irgacure 2959 (BASF SE, Ludwigshafen, Germany) was used to crosslink GMHA and MAHA. Irgacure 2959 was prepared by dissolving in 1X PBS at a concentration of 10 mg/mL and sonicating at 40°C until dissolved. GMHA or MAHA was then dissolved in Irgacure

solution at the appropriate concentration to produce the final mixtures. Hydrogel solutions containing GMHA or MAHA were UV crosslinked at $\sim 12 \text{ mW/cm}^2$ for 5 minutes.

Chemical Analysis (HNMR)

The degree of methacrylation was calculated by using proton NMR spectroscopy for both GMHA and MAHA samples. NMR spectra were obtained using a 600 MHz Bruker Avance III spectrophotometer (Bruker, Billerica, MA). Deuterium oxide (Cambridge Isotope Laboratories, Tewksbury, MA) was used as a solvent and analysis was performed at room temperature. The relative peak integration was performed between methacrylate protons (peak at 1.8) and methyl protons already present on the HA backbone (peak at 1.9) to determine the ratio of methacrylate groups to HA monomers. This is referenced throughout the paper as “degree of methacrylation” to mean the percentage of HA monomers containing methacrylated groups.

Isolation of Rat Tissue

Isolation of rat tissue as described here was approved by the Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee (IACUC) at the University of Florida. To obtain tissues, three rats were perfused with PBS to remove blood and then the following tissues were harvested and used for mechanical testing: sciatic nerve, spinal cord, brain, tibialis anterior (TA) muscle, kidney, spleen, heart, liver, and lung tissue. The tissue was removed and immediately tested using the indentation procedure described below.

Swelling Assessment

A swelling study was used to characterize various hydrogels used in this study for swell ratio, average molecular weight between crosslinks, and mesh size. Briefly, both single-component methacrylated HA and triple-component hydrogels were fabricated as described above. After fabrication, hydrogels were swollen in PBS for 24 hours to allow for swelling equilibrium in PBS to be reached. Hydrogels were then weighed and their mass recorded. Hydrogels were then placed in pre-weighed microcentrifuge tubes, flash frozen in liquid nitrogen, and lyophilized for 3 days. The weight of the microcentrifuge tubes were weighed once again and the initial tube masses were subtracted to get the dry mass of the hydrogels.

Flory-Rehner calculations were used as described by Leach, et al. ⁽⁷⁾ to determine the average molecular weight between crosslinks and mesh size. Briefly, the degree of mass swelling (Q_M) was determined by the ratio of swollen hydrogel mass to dry polymer mass:

$$Q_M = \frac{M_e}{M_D}$$

Then, degree of volumetric swelling (Q_V) was calculated as follows:

$$Q_V = 1 + \frac{\rho_p}{\rho_s}(Q_M - 1)$$

Where ρ_p is the dry polymer density (estimated to be 1.229 g/cm³ for HA⁽⁷⁾) and ρ_s is the density of the solvent, water. Finally, we use the adapted Flory-Rehner equation described in⁽⁷⁾ to get the average molecular weight between crosslinks, \bar{M}_c :

$$Q_V^{5/3} \cong \frac{\bar{v}\bar{M}_c}{V_1} \left(\frac{1}{2} - \chi \right)$$

Where \bar{v} is the specific volume of the dry polymer, V_1 is the molar volume of the solvent, and χ is the Flory polymer-solvent interaction parameter. χ is estimated to be 0.473, as described in⁽⁷⁾. The following equation was used to determine the swollen hydrogel mesh size, ξ , the derivation of this equation is described in⁽⁷⁾:

$$\xi = 0.1748 \sqrt{\bar{M}_c Q_V}^{1/3}$$

As noted in⁽⁷⁾, assumptions were made in these calculations, however they still reflect the real differences between the various hydrogels that were tested even if there may be some slight differences in the calculated values and real values.

Mechanical Analysis (Indentation)

Indentation was performed using a custom cantilever-based indentation system built by Dr. Chelsey Simmons' group at UF (38),(39). A piezoelectric stage (P-628.1CD, Physik Instrumente) was used to control the base of a cantilever with a rigid tip. A custom LabVIEW program (National Instruments, Austin, TX) reads tip deflection with a capacitive sensor (C8S-3.2-2.0 and compact driver CD1-CD6; Lion Precision, St. Paul, MN). Eight mm diameter, 2 mm height cylindrical samples were prepared by pipetting hydrogel solution into silicone molds (Grace Bio-Labs 622305). Tissue samples were cut into similar dimensions using an 8 mm diameter tissue punch. Hydrogels or tissue samples were loaded into the indentation device and indented with a 4 mm hemispherical ruby probe to a depth of 200 μm (10% of 2 mm sample thickness). Samples were hydrated with PBS to decrease adhesion between the probe and the surface of the sample. Indentation rate was 10 $\mu\text{m/s}$ and the relaxation phase was 20 s. A rearrangement of the Hertz contact model was used to obtain a transient modulus, and the relaxation stage was fit to the standard linear solid model to obtain the Steady-State Modulus (SSM), the effective modulus after relaxation(38),(39). For details and discussion of this method, see reference (37).

In Vitro Evaluation

For in vitro testing, hydrogel solutions were mixed as described in the Hydrogel Synthesis section and 150 μL was pipetted into a 24-well plate under sterile conditions. If the solution contained collagen and/or laminin, it was incubated at 37°C for 30 minutes followed by 5 minutes under UV if the solution contained GMHA or MAHA.

Schwann cells and DRGs were cultured on 6 different hydrogels, including 20X GMHA and 10X MAHA at concentrations of 5 mg/mL, triple-component gels with either GMHA or MAHA plus collagen I and laminin, collagen I alone, and collagen I plus laminin.

Schwann Cell Culture—Schwann cells (SCs) were purchased from ScienCell (Carlsbad, CA) and thawed based on the manufacturer's protocol. Cells were expanded in culture medium consisting of Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (Fisher Scientific), 10% fetal bovine serum (Atlanta Biologicals, Flowery Branch, GA), 1% Gibco penicillin-streptomycin (Fisher Scientific), 0.1% forskolin, 0.14% bovine pituitary extract (Fisher Scientific), and 0.2% fibroblast growth factor (Fisher Scientific)^{(40),(41)}. SCs (passage 4) were seeded at a density of 1.5×10^4 cells per well on hydrogels pre-made in 24-well plates and incubated for 3 days in a humidified incubator at 37°C and 5% CO₂. Media was changed after each alamarBlue reading.

Cell metabolic activity assay—Metabolic activity as a proxy for cell proliferation was measured at day one and three, using alamarBlue Cell Viability Reagent (Fisher Scientific) based on the manufacturer's instructions. Briefly, 300 µL of media with 10% volume of alamarBlue replaced the cell culture media and the cells were further incubated for 4 hours. Hydrogel without cells served as the blank. Supernatant was removed from the dishes and moved to a 96 well plate followed by absorbance readings at 600 nm wavelength. The percentage change in cell activity between day 1 and 3 was quantified and compared between hydrogels (n=3).

DRGs Isolation and Culture—DRGs were isolated from neonatal Sprague-Dawley green fluorescent protein (GFP)-positive rats (Charles River, Wilmington, MA). DRGs were stored in hibernate medium (Hibernate A media (BrainBits, Springfield, IL), 1% 50X B-27 supplement (Fisher Scientific), 1% Glutamax) for up to 7 days following extraction from rats. DRG neurites were trimmed and DRGs were placed inside 30 µL hydrogel droplets, followed by hydrogel crosslinking as described above. DRG culture medium was composed of 1X Neurobasal medium (Gibco, Fisher Scientific), 0.9% Glutamax, 0.9% B-27, 0.9% penicillin-streptomycin-amphotericin B 100X (Fisher Scientific), 10% fetal bovine serum, and 0.01% NGF. Media was added to each well and incubated in a humidified incubator at 37°C and 5% CO₂ for 3 days. Media were changed every other day.

Measuring DRG neurite outgrowth—After 3 days of culture, GFP-positive DRGs were imaged using an Axio Imager 2 (Zeiss, Oberkochen, Germany). ImageJ and the neurite tracer plugin⁽⁴²⁾ were used to quantify lengths of the neurites extending from the DRGs. Up to 10 neurite extensions were measured from each DRG (many DRGs had no neurite extensions, as described in the results; n=3). These results were then averaged for DRGs cultured in each hydrogel type.

Statistics

The statistics package GraphPad Prism (GraphPad Software Inc., San Diego, CA) was used for statistical analysis. ANOVA and Tukey's test were used to compare results among the different hydrogels. Significance was considered for p values less than 0.05

Results

HNMR

The presence of peaks at 5.6 and 6.1 confirms the methacrylation of the HA backbone for both GMHA and MAHA, Figure 1. The relative integration between methacrylate protons (peak at 1.8) and methyl protons already present on the HA backbone (peak at 1.9) was used to determine the degree of methacrylation for GMHA and MAHA ^{(7),(25)}. GMHA fabricated with stoichiometric ratios of glycidyl methacrylate to HA monomer of 5X, 10X, and 20X had methacrylation of 2.4, 6, and 16%, respectively, whereas for MAHA, 5X, 10X, 20X, and 40X had 10, 30, 53, and 86% methacrylation, respectively (Table 1).

Swelling experiment

As described in the Methods section, swelling ratio was calculated and Flory-Rehner calculations were used to determine the mesh size and the average molecular weight between crosslinks. For all swelling test results following ANOVA and multiple comparisons, there were two cohorts that were significantly different from each other. One cohort contained 6% and 16% GMHA and 10% and 30% MAHA. The second cohort included 50% and 86% MAHA, plus triple-component MAHA and GMHA. Swelling ratio tended to decrease with increased methacrylation. HA with 30% or less methacrylation had swelling ratios greater than 100, while HA with 50% or greater methacrylation had swelling ratios of under 80.

Mesh size had a similar trend with HA with 30% or lower methacrylation having a mesh size of greater than 1000 nm while HA with higher methacrylation had smaller mesh size. Average molecular weight between crosslinks reflected the same trend. HA with 30% or lower methacrylation had higher molecular weight between crosslinks than HA with higher methacrylation. This is as expected because the higher methacrylation results in more crosslinks being formed.

Mechanical testing

Indentation was performed on GMHA and MAHA with either varied concentration (16% GMHA and 30% MAHA; from 5 to 15 mg/mL) or with constant concentration (5 mg/mL) but changing degrees of methacrylation, Figure 3. Increased concentration resulted in an increase in modulus with GMHA modulus increasing from 2.28 ± 0.15 to 4.00 ± 0.26 to 4.81 ± 0.29 kPa with increased concentrations of 5, 10, and 15 mg/mL, respectively, Figure 3A. For MAHA, modulus increased from 4.70 ± 0.21 to 6.13 ± 0.44 kPa with concentrations of 5 and 10 mg/mL, respectively, Figure 3A. At concentrations above 10 mg/mL with 30% MAHA, the solution does not fully dissolve, so hydrogels cannot be properly formed.

When concentration was held constant at 5 mg/mL, the modulus increases with degree of methacrylation. 6% and 16% GMHA gels had moduli of 1.22 ± 0.07 and 2.28 ± 0.15 kPa, respectively. 2.4% GMHA was too soft to measure on the indentation device. MAHA with 10%, 30%, and 53% methacrylation exhibited increasing moduli of 2.23 ± 0.18 , 4.70 ± 0.21 , and 5.83 ± 0.20 kPa, Figure 3B-C. However, at 86% methacrylation, the modulus plateaued at 5.36 ± 0.07 kPa and was not significantly different from 50% MAHA.

To show the versatility of mechanical properties obtainable with methacrylated HA, they were compared to a wide variety of soft tissues from rats. These tissues include tibialis anterior (TA) muscle, sciatic nerve, kidney, spleen, heart, liver, brain, spinal cord, and lung. The tissue with the highest modulus was TA muscle at 4.28 ± 0.51 kPa and the lowest modulus was lung at 0.31 ± 0.04 kPa, Figure 4. The highest modulus obtained with methacrylated HA was 50% MAHA at 5 mg/mL with a modulus of 6.13 ± 0.44 kPa and the lowest was 6% GMHA at 3 mg/mL with a modulus of 0.35 ± 0.05 kPa, Figure 4.

To show the versatility to both mimic native ECM and match mechanical properties, GMHA and MAHA were then combined with collagen I and laminin to form nerve-ECM-mimicking triple-component hydrogels. Rat sciatic nerve was found to have a modulus of 2.47 ± 0.31 kPa. Collagen I and collagen I plus laminin gels were fabricated as control groups. Triple-component GMHA (5 mg/ml with 16% methacrylation) and MAHA (5 mg/ml with 30% methacrylation) were not significantly different from sciatic nerve with moduli of 2.55 ± 0.05 kPa and 2.91 ± 0.19 kPa, respectively, Figure 6. The modulus of collagen I was significantly below that of sciatic nerve (0.83 ± 0.06 kPa, $p < 0.0001$), as was the modulus of collagen and laminin combined (0.76 ± 0.02 kPa, $p < 0.0001$).

In vitro

Schwann Cell Viability in Hydrogels—AlamarBlue assays were performed on days 1 and 3 following Schwann cell culture on hydrogels. Cell metabolic activity changes the absorbance of the alamarBlue reagent through a chemical reduction reaction that can be quantified using a spectrophotometer. The % chemical reduction of the alamarBlue reagent correlates directly with the intensity of the absorbance at a wavelength of 600 nm and cell metabolic activity. Cell metabolic activity was quantified on day 1 and day 3. Metabolic activity at day 3 was normalized against day 1 to reveal the changes between the time points, Figure 7. GMHA and MAHA without additional components show a major decrease in cell activity whereas all other hydrogels had an increase in cell activity. The % change in cell activity from day 1 to 3 was -15% and -24% for GMHA and MAHA. However, the addition of collagen I and laminin resulted in a 5% and 7% increase, respectively, whereas collagen I and collagen I plus laminin had increases of 5% and 9% , respectively. As expected, metabolic activity increased over 3 days for hydrogels containing adhesive components such as collagen and/or laminin but decreased without these adhesive proteins.

DRG Neurite Extensions—DRGs cultured in GMHA or MAHA without other ECM components had no neurite extensions in every hydrogel. As expected, DRGs cultured in hydrogels without HA but with collagen I and/or laminin reveal robust neurite extensions with average neurite lengths ranging from $310 \mu\text{m}$ for triple component MAHA to $530 \mu\text{m}$ for collagen + laminin, Figure 8. (Note: images of GFP-positive DRGs was inversed to aid with viewability.) There was a statistically significant difference between hydrogels containing cell adhesive proteins (collagen and/or laminin) and those without (GMHA or MAHA alone).

Discussion

In this study, we provide a side-by-side comparison of a range of degrees of methacrylation and concentrations for hyaluronic acid hydrogels, using two different methacrylation chemistries. We characterized these hydrogels using an indentation technique that has been designed specifically for soft materials and compared these hydrogels to a range of soft tissues from rat, also characterized using the same indentation approach. Combination of the HA hydrogels with collagen and laminin were shown to promote cell attachment as previously known, but we show that crosslinked HA is required as a backbone to match the mechanics of native tissue. The goal of these studies was to collate data for multiple HA hydrogels into a single study using uniform and consistent methodologies as a resource for those working in the field. We also provide anecdotal insights into working with the different hydrogel systems, again, with the intent of providing a resource to those working in this area, and to encourage other researchers to adapt HA as a flexible biomaterial platform.

Many biomaterials in the form of hydrogels, both synthetic and/or natural, have been investigated for use in tissue engineering. For synthetic materials, PEG and PLA copolymers have been studied for their degradation profiles for drug delivery systems and cell encapsulation⁽⁴³⁾. Although synthetic materials are commonly used and generally highly tunable, they lack some of the advantages of using natural biomaterials such as ECM-mimicking mechanical properties and presence of cell adhesive peptide sequences which must be added synthetically, similar to HA. Researchers using natural ECM-based hydrogels have predominantly focused on collagen I because of its ubiquity throughout tissue and its natural crosslinking capabilities⁽⁴⁴⁾. However, HA-based hydrogels are of particular interest because they are also of natural origin and mimic GAG polymer chains, which are extensively found within soft tissue such as neural tissues. HA-based hydrogels are also highly tunable for a broad range of biodegradability rates and mechanical properties^{(25),(27),(45)}. Here, we have provided a direct side-by-side comparison of two HA methacrylation techniques that illustrates a broad range of mechanical properties are possible covering a broad range of soft tissues.

A swelling experiment was used to quantify the hydrogel mesh size and average molecular weight between crosslinks. The mesh size and molecular weight between crosslinks both tended to decrease with increased methacrylation. This is expected because the presence of more methacrylate groups means more sites for crosslinking. Hydrogels that had collagen and laminin tended to be more similar to the higher methacrylate HA rather than the actual HA methacrylation present in these hydrogels. There are a number of potential explanations for this, one is that because the collagen and HA form an interpenetrating polymer network, the swelling capacity of these hydrogels is more similar to that of HA with a higher number of crosslinks.

The number and density of crosslink groups of HA-based hydrogels is also a way to modify the mechanical properties of these hydrogels. The long polysaccharide chains of HA have functional groups (carboxyl and hydroxyl) for covalent modification such as adding methacrylate groups. Such modification allows for controlling the hydrogel's crosslink density, which leads to tunable mechanical properties and degradation rates^{(24),(46)}. We

showed, as have others ^{(7),(45),(47)}, that the increase in degree of methacrylation (i.e., percentage of HA monomers containing methacrylate groups) resulted from increasing stoichiometric amount of methacrylate precursors (methacrylic anhydride for MAHA and glycidyl methacrylate for GMHA). This directly leads to increased modulus in mechanical properties of the hydrogel. Here we show GMHA had significantly lower effective modulus than MAHA hydrogels at similar concentrations and degree of methacrylation. Increasing the degree of methacrylation correlated with an increase in modulus consistent with previous studies ^{(27),(45),(48)} until 86% MAHA. At 86% MAHA, the modulus plateaued relative to 50% MAHA suggesting there is an upper limit to how % methacrylation affects the mechanical properties of these hydrogels. The corresponding figure, Figure 3C, shows that the relationship between the modulus and the % methacrylation resembles an S-curve with the plateau after 50% MAHA. Hydrogels without methacrylated HA tended to have the lowest modulus, i.e. those composed of only collagen I or with collagen I and laminin.

Another way to modify mechanical properties is modulating the dissolved concentration of methacrylated HA. There are limitations to this however and a combination of tuning the degree of methacrylation and concentration may be necessary. Here, we dissolved GMHA and MAHA at concentrations ranging from 5 mg/mL to 15 mg/mL in solution. As expected, higher concentrations of HA resulted in a higher effective modulus for both GMHA and MAHA. There are two limiting factors when modulating the mechanical properties of GMHA or MAHA by changing the concentration. One is the upper limit of the amount of material that can be dissolved in solution. For example, MAHA was not tested above concentrations of 10 mg/mL because the MAHA will not fully dissolve in solution with higher concentrations. The other limitation is solution viscosity. As concentration of HA is increased, so is solution viscosity. At a certain point (approximately 20 mg/mL for 16% GMHA), the solution becomes too viscous to pipette, limiting the ability to consistently form hydrogels. Although this may not be a limitation for certain uses of GMHA, it does limit the ability to form hydrogels for mechanical testing.

As shown in Figure 3, modulating either concentration of HA or degree of methacrylation have similar effects on the final mechanical properties of the hydrogel. However, changing the degree of methacrylation allows for a wider range of potential mechanical properties. Bencherif, et al. (2008) demonstrated the ability to fabricate GMHA with a degree of methacrylation as high as 90% ⁽⁴⁷⁾ relative to our 16% methacrylation for GMHA and the similar 86% methacrylation for MAHA. The authors obtained GMHA hydrogels with shear modulus ranging from 16 to 65 kPa by modulating degree of methacrylation. They also noted that at higher degrees of methacrylation, the effects on mechanical properties are diminished. For example, going from 60% to 90% methacrylation does not result in a significant increase in shear modulus, despite the 50% increase in the number of crosslink groups. This is consistent with our results showing an increase from 53 to 86% methacrylation did not result in any increase in the modulus, confirming that mechanical properties plateau with increasing crosslink groups.

Changing the concentration and/or the degree of methacrylation to modulate mechanical properties resulted in a range of mechanical properties spanning an order of magnitude from ~0.3 kPa to ~6 kPa, allowing for use with a range of soft tissues beyond the neural

tissues demonstrated in this study. Here, we demonstrated this by using the same indentation technique to measure the modulus of a wide variety of soft tissues from rat. All tissues tested were within the range of what is mechanically possible with GMHA or MAHA. In addition, these hydrogels could be modulated mechanically and then mixed with other ECM proteins to match many other soft tissues such as cornea⁽⁴⁹⁾, skeletal muscle⁽⁵⁰⁾, and other neural tissues like brain⁽⁵¹⁾, among other soft tissues⁽⁵²⁾.

Beyond mechanical properties, there are other factors that should be noted when designing a methacrylated HA-based hydrogel, such as ease of synthesis. While this is largely anecdotal, we note that GMHA is typically easier to synthesize than MAHA with the chemistries we have used here. As noted in the Methods, the GMHA synthesis step consists of adding triethylamine to the HA solution followed by glycidyl methacrylate 30 minutes later at the correct stoichiometric ratio. MAHA however requires the stepwise addition of methacrylic anhydride all while using NaOH to keep the pH between 8 to 11. While this is a very wide pH range, the pH can fluctuate substantially with the addition of methacrylic anhydride. In addition, the MAHA solution tends to be very viscous as the solution is kept on ice, so proper mixing after addition of methacrylic anhydride or NaOH. We have found that the process of synthesizing GMHA makes it easy to produce up to five GMHA batches at a time because they can all be done at once, whereas MAHA can only be done one batch at a time and is already a more time-consuming synthesis step than GMHA.

Our results show GMHA and MAHA alone do not support cell metabolic activity because of the lack of adhesion. Although HA hydrogel mimics GAG chains, this system needs additional adhesive components (such as collagen, laminin, or fibronectin) to facilitate the ability of cell adhesion and migration. Collagen I and laminin alone resulted in hydrogels that were unable to match the mechanical properties of native nerve tissue, Figure 6. We showed addition of collagen I and laminin resulted in lower mechanical modulus for both GMHA and MAHA triple-component hydrogels relative to methacrylated HA alone, however this did overcome the adhesion problem associated with HA hydrogels⁽²¹⁾. This decrease can possibly be explained by collagen and laminin interfering with the crosslinking of the methacrylate groups on the modified HA. This is expected as these hydrogels are formed by entanglement of collagen fibrils rather than the chemical crosslinks formed via methacrylation. This range of mechanical properties has important implications for the usefulness of methacrylated HA.

As expected, the hydrogels containing ECM proteins demonstrate enhanced biocompatibility. Metabolic activity of Schwann cells increased in all gels containing collagen I and laminin, likely because collagen I and laminin contain adhesive peptide sequences such as RGD and YIGSR that facilitate cell adherence in the first few hours after cell seeding^{(44),(53),(54)}. In addition to the mechanical tunability of the hydrogels, triple-component hydrogels performed as well as collagen and collagen/laminin hydrogels in promoting DRG neurite extension and Schwann cell activity in vitro indicating that the change in mechanical properties did not inhibit cell growth or neurite extension. Though these triple-component hydrogels tended to match the biological activity of the hydrogels with just collagen and/or laminin, methacrylated HA provides the mechanical tunability

discussed throughout this paper in addition to HA's own biological advantages such as its role in wound healing and its use in neural regeneration ⁽⁵⁾.

These triple-component hydrogels have a number of potential uses in addition to being used as pro-regenerative scaffolds. There has been increased interest in developing lab-on-a-chip and in vitro testing platforms to reduce the need for in vivo studies which face a number of economic and ethical constraints. Although many different lab-on-a-chip platforms have been developed, most do not have ECM-mimicking qualities ⁽⁵⁵⁾. These testing platforms require biomaterials that recapitulate the ECM composition and mechanical properties of native tissue. The majority of lab-on-a-chip platforms for neural tissue are polydimethylsiloxane-based, which are mechanically much stiffer than neural tissues. Some, such as AxoSim, allow for integration of a hydrogel with organoids or DRGs ⁽⁵⁶⁾. HA has the benefits of both natural biomaterials (with its biocompatibility and native role in vivo) and synthetic materials (by being tunable), and therefore it is ideally suited for such technologies. The hydrogels we have studied here could be used with platforms such as AxoSim to have a mechanically-tuned and ECM-mimicking lab-on-a-chip ^{(56),(57)}. The development of these platforms means various drug or other therapies can be tested in an in vivo-mimicking environment without the limitations of animal studies. Because of the ubiquity of HA in nearly all soft tissues, methacrylated HA can provide a starting point for mixing with other ECM components while mechanically tuning to that of the desired native tissue ⁽²¹⁾.

Another potential application for these hydrogels is 3D bioprinting ⁽⁵⁸⁾. Bioprinting allows for custom-made, tunable, and complex regenerative scaffolds for tissues including skin, cartilage, heart valve, and kidneys, among other tissue ^{(59),(60)}. Work has previously been performed on both methacrylated gelatin ⁽⁶¹⁾ and HA with various modifications ^{(58),(62)}. Thiolated HA, along with modified polyethylene glycol, was used to print vessel-like structures ⁽⁶³⁾. Researchers have developed other modified HA to be suitable for bioprinting including hydrazide or aldehyde modification ⁽⁶⁴⁾. Methacrylated HA with other ECM components such as collagen I and laminin is a potential bioink platform for neural bioprinting for reasons mentioned above including HA's ubiquity in soft tissue and tunability.

We used neural cells (Schwann cells and DRGs) to demonstrate the in vitro uses for these hydrogels because these materials have been used many times for these applications. For example, Suri, et al. demonstrated custom nerve mimicking GMHA-based hydrogels for peripheral nerve tissue engineering ⁽⁶⁵⁾. The triple-component hydrogels used in this study are also the hydrogels used for early iterations of our tissue-engineered electronic nerve interface project ⁽⁶⁶⁾⁻⁽⁶⁸⁾.

Overall, methacrylation of HA and addition of other ECM components can be mechanically and compositionally tuned to numerous soft tissues, beyond peripheral nerve. Applications could include tissue-engineered hydrogel scaffolds, in vitro testing platforms, and as a 3D bioprinting material.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have demonstrated that a wide range of mechanical properties of methacrylated HA is possible covering a wide range of soft tissues. In addition, these hydrogels can be easily modulated by the addition of other ECM components. Here, we specifically demonstrate a nerve-mimicking hydrogel with components found in the native ECM, collagen I and laminin, in addition to the modified HA. Methacrylated HA can provide a tunable platform for design of complex ECM-mimicking scaffolds for a wide variety of soft tissue engineering applications.

Acknowledgements

The HNMR work was supported in part by an NIH award, S10RR031637, for magnetic resonance instrumentation. HNMR work was performed in the McKnight Brain Institute at the National High Magnetic Field Laboratory's AMRIS Facility, which is supported by National Science Foundation Cooperative Agreement Nos. DMR-1157490 and DMR-1644779 and the State of Florida.

References

1. Khademhosseini A, Langer R, Borenstein J, Vacanti JP. Microscale technologies for tissue engineering and biology. *Proc Natl Acad Sci.* 2006;103:2480–7. [PubMed: 16477028]
2. Drury JL, Mooney DJ. Hydrogels for tissue engineering: Scaffold design variables and applications. *Biomaterials.* 2003;24:4337–51. [PubMed: 12922147]
3. Geckil H, Xu F, Zhang X, Moon S, Demirci U. Engineering hydrogels as extracellular matrix mimics. *Nanomedicine.* 2010;5:469–84. [PubMed: 20394538]
4. Kleinman HK, Martin GR. Matrigel: Basement membrane matrix with biological activity. *Semin Cancer Biol.* 2005;15:378–86. [PubMed: 15975825]
5. Wang K-K, Nemeth IR, Seckel BR, Chakalis-Haley DP, Swann DA, Kuo J-W, Bryan DJ, Cetrulo CL. Hyaluronic acid enhances peripheral nerve regeneration in vivo. *Microsurgery.* 1998;18:270–5. [PubMed: 9779641]
6. Lam J, Truong NF, Segura T. Design of cell-matrix interactions in hyaluronic acid hydrogel scaffolds. *Acta Biomater. Acta Materialia Inc.;* 2014;10:1571–80. [PubMed: 23899481]
7. Leach JB, Bivens KA, Patrick CW, Schmidt CE. Photocrosslinked hyaluronic acid hydrogels: Natural, biodegradable tissue engineering scaffolds. *Biotechnol Bioeng.* 2003;82:578–89. [PubMed: 12652481]
8. Fraser JRE, Laurent TC, Laurent UBG. Hyaluronan: its nature, distribution, functions and turnover. *J Intern Med.* 1997;242:27–33. [PubMed: 9260563]
9. Monslow J, Govindaraju P, Puré E. Hyaluronan – a functional and structural sweet spot in the tissue microenvironment. *Front Immunol.* 2015;6:1–19. [PubMed: 25657648]
10. Laurent TC. Studies on hyaluronic acid in the vitreous body. *J Biol Chem.* 1955;216:263–71. [PubMed: 13252026]
11. Hardingham TE, Muir H. The specific interaction of hyaluronic acid with cartilage proteoglycans. *BBA - Gen Subj.* 1972;279:401–5.
12. Lander AD. Proteoglycans in the nervous system. *Curr Opin Neurobiol.* 1993;3:716–23. [PubMed: 8260820]
13. Cowman MK, Lee H-G, Schwertfeger KL, McCarthy JB, Turley EA. The content and size of hyaluronan in biological fluids and tissues. *Front Immunol.* 2015;6:1–8. [PubMed: 25657648]
14. Kogan G, Šoltés L, Stern R, Gemeiner P. Hyaluronic acid: a natural biopolymer with a broad range of biomedical and industrial applications. *Biotechnol Lett.* 2007;29:17–25. [PubMed: 17091377]
15. Chen C-H, Wang S-S, Wei EI, Chu T-Y, Hsieh PCH. Hyaluronan enhances bone marrow cell therapy for myocardial repair after infarction. *Mol Ther.* 2013;21:670–9. [PubMed: 23295948]

16. Wei YT, He Y, Xu CL, Wang Y, Liu BF, Wang XM, Sun XD, Cui FZ, Xu QY. Hyaluronic acid hydrogel modified with nogo-66 receptor antibody and poly-L-lysine to promote axon regrowth after spinal cord injury. *J Biomed Mater Res - Part B Appl Biomater.* 2010;95:110–7.
17. Lin CM, Lin JW, Chen YC, Shen HH, Wei L, Yeh YS, Chiang YH, Shih R, Chiu PL, Hung KS, Yang LY, Chiu WT. Hyaluronic acid inhibits the glial scar formation after brain damage with tissue loss in rats. *Surg Neurol.* 2009;72.
18. Seckel BR, Jones D, Hekimian KJ, Wang K-K, Chakalis DP, Costas PD. Hyaluronic acid through a new injectable nerve guide delivery system enhances peripheral nerve regeneration in the rat. *J Neurosci Res.* 1995;40:318–24. [PubMed: 7745625]
19. Agerup Berg, Akermark C. Non-Animal Stabilized Hyaluronic Acid. *BioDrugs.* 2005;19:23–30. [PubMed: 15691214]
20. Burdick JA, Prestwich GD. Hyaluronic acid hydrogels for biomedical applications. *Adv Mater.* 2011;23:41–56.
21. Collins MN, Birkinshaw C. Hyaluronic acid based scaffolds for tissue engineering - A review. *Carbohydr Polym.* Elsevier Ltd.; 2013;92:1262–79. [PubMed: 23399155]
22. Schanté CE, Zuber G, Herlin C, Vandamme TF. Chemical modifications of hyaluronic acid for the synthesis of derivatives for a broad range of biomedical applications. *Carbohydr Polym.* 2011;85:469–89.
23. Shu XZ, Liu Y, Palumbo FS, Luo Y, Prestwich GD. In situ crosslinkable hyaluronan hydrogels for tissue engineering. *Biomaterials.* 2004;25:1339–48. [PubMed: 14643608]
24. Suri S, Schmidt CE. Photopatterned collagen-hyaluronic acid interpenetrating polymer network hydrogels. *Acta Biomater. Acta Materialia Inc.;* 2009;5:2385–97. [PubMed: 19446050]
25. Seidlits SK, Khaing ZZ, Petersen RR, Nickels JD, Vanscoy JE, Shear JB, Schmidt CE. The effects of hyaluronic acid hydrogels with tunable mechanical properties on neural progenitor cell differentiation. *Biomaterials.* Elsevier Ltd; 2010;31:3930–40. [PubMed: 20171731]
26. Tibbitt MW, Anseth KS. Hydrogels as extracellular matrix mimics for 3D cell culture. *Biotechnol Bioeng.* 2009.
27. Burdick JA, Chung C, Jia X, Randolph MA, Langer R. Controlled degradation and mechanical behavior of photopolymerized hyaluronic acid networks. *Biomacromolecules.* 2005;6:386–91. [PubMed: 15638543]
28. Deister C, Aljabari S, Schmidt CE. Effects of collagen 1, fibronectin, laminin and hyaluronic acid concentration in multi-component gels on neurite extension. *J Biomater Sci Polym Ed.* 2007;18:983–97. [PubMed: 17705994]
29. Chen ZL, Strickland S. Laminin $\gamma 1$ is critical for Schwann cell differentiation, axon myelination, and regeneration in the peripheral nerve. *J Cell Biol.* 2003;163:889–99. [PubMed: 14638863]
30. Yu X, Bellamkonda RV. Dorsal Root Ganglia Neurite Extension Is Inhibited by Mechanical and Chondroitin Sulfate-Rich Interfaces. *J Neurosci Res.* 2001;66:303–10. [PubMed: 11592128]
31. Balgude AP, Yu X, Szymanski A, Bellamkonda RV. Agarose gel stiffness determines rate of DRG neurite extension in 3D cultures. *Biomaterials.* 2001;22:1077–84. [PubMed: 11352088]
32. Pelham RJ Jr., Wang Y-L. Cell locomotion and focal adhesions are regulated by. *Proc Natl Acad Sci.* 1997;94:13661–5. [PubMed: 9391082]
33. Ahearne M, Yang Y, Liu K-K. Mechanical Characterisation of Hydrogels for Tissue Engineering Applications. *Top Tissue Eng.* 2008.
34. Lapasin R Rheological Characterization of Hydrogels. In: Matricardi P, Alhaique F, Coviello T editors. *Polysacch Hydrogels Charact Biomed Appl.* 2016.
35. Zuidema JM, Rivet CJ, Gilbert RJ, Morrison FA. A protocol for rheological characterization of hydrogels for tissue engineering strategies. *J Biomed Mater Res - Part B Appl Biomater.* 2014;102:1063–73.
36. Oyen ML. Mechanical characterisation of hydrogel materials. *Int Mater Rev.* 2014;59:44–59.
37. Rubiano A, Galitz C, Simmons CS. Mechanical characterization by mesoscale indentation: Advantages & pitfalls for tissue and scaffolds. *Tissue Eng Part C.* 2018;1–45.

38. Rubiano A, Delitto D, Han S, Gerber M, Galitz C, Trevino J, Thomas RM, Hughes SJ, Simmons CS. Viscoelastic properties of human pancreatic tumors and in vitro constructs to mimic mechanical properties. *Acta Biomater.* 2018;67.
39. Stewart DC, Rubiano A, Dyson K, Simmons CS. Mechanical characterization of human brain tumors from patients and comparison to potential surgical phantoms. *PLoS One.* 2017;12:1–19.
40. Haastert K, Mauritz C, Chaturvedi S, Grothe C. Human and rat adult Schwann cell cultures: fast and efficient enrichment and highly effective non-viral transfection protocol. *Nat Protoc.* 2007;2:99–104. [PubMed: 17401343]
41. Kaewkhaw R, Scutt AM, Haycock JW. Integrated culture and purification of rat Schwann cells from freshly isolated adult tissue. *Nat Protoc.* 2012;7:1996–2004. [PubMed: 23060244]
42. Longair MH, Baker DA, Armstrong JD. Simple neurite tracer: Open source software for reconstruction, visualization and analysis of neuronal processes. *Bioinformatics.* 2011;27:2453–4. [PubMed: 21727141]
43. Metters AT, Anseth KS, Bowman CN. Fundamental studies of a novel, biodegradable PEG-b-PLA hydrogel. *Polymer (Guildf).* 2000;41:3993–4004.
44. Antoine EE, Vlachos PP, Rylander MN. Review of Collagen I Hydrogels for Bioengineered Tissue Microenvironments: Characterization of Mechanics, Structure, and Transport. *Tissue Eng Part B Rev.* 2014;20:683–96. [PubMed: 24923709]
45. Tavsanli B, Can V, Okay O. Mechanically strong triple network hydrogels based on hyaluronan and poly(N,N-dimethylacrylamide). *Soft Matter. Royal Society of Chemistry;* 2015;11:8517–24. [PubMed: 26376837]
46. Hoffman AS. Hydrogels for biomedical applications. *Adv Drug Deliv Rev. Elsevier B.V.;* 2012;64:18–23.
47. Bencherif SA, Srinivasan A, Horkay F, Hollinger JO, Matyjaszewski K, Washburn NR. Influence of the degree of methacrylation on hyaluronic acid hydrogels properties. *Biomaterials.* 2008;29:1739–49. [PubMed: 18234331]
48. Hachet E, Van Den Berghe H, Bayma E, Block MR, Auzély-Velty R. Design of biomimetic cell-interactive substrates using hyaluronic acid hydrogels with tunable mechanical properties. *Biomacromolecules.* 2012;13:1818–27. [PubMed: 22559074]
49. Rafat M, Li F, Fagerholm P, Lagali NS, Watsky MA, Munger R, Matsuura T, Griffith M. PEG-stabilized carbodiimide crosslinked collagen-chitosan hydrogels for corneal tissue engineering. *Biomaterials.* 2008;29:3960–72. [PubMed: 18639928]
50. Engler AJ, Griffin MA, Sen S, Bönnemann CG, Sweeney HL, Discher DE. Myotubes differentiate optimally on substrates with tissue-like stiffness: Pathological implications for soft or stiff microenvironments. *J Cell Biol.* 2004;166:877–87. [PubMed: 15364962]
51. Miller K, Chinzei K, Orssengo G, Bednarz P. Mechanical properties of brain tissue in-vivo: experiment and computer simulation. *J Biomech.* 2000;33:1369–76. [PubMed: 10940395]
52. Levental I, Georges PC, Janmey PA. Soft biological materials and their impact on cell function. *Soft Matter.* 2007;3:299–306. [PubMed: 32900146]
53. McKerracher L, Chamoux M, Arregui CO. Role of laminin and integrin interactions in growth cone guidance. *Mol Neurobiol.* 1996;12:95–116. [PubMed: 8818145]
54. Koopmans G, Hasse B, Sinis N. The Role of Collagen in Peripheral Nerve Repair. *Int Rev Neurobiol.* 2009.
55. Mobini S, Song YH, McCrary MW, Schmidt CE. Advances in ex vivo models and lab-on-a-chip devices for neural tissue engineering. *Biomaterials. Elsevier Ltd;* 2018;
56. Huval RM, Miller OH, Curley JL, Fan Y, Hall J, Moore MJ. Microengineered peripheral nerve-on-a-chip for preclinical physiological testing. *Lab Chip. Royal Society of Chemistry;* 2015;15:2221–32.
57. Xu G, Tan Y, Xu T, Yin D, Wang M, Shen M, Chen X, Shi X, Zhu X. Hyaluronic acid-functionalized electrospun PLGA nanofibers embedded in a microfluidic chip for cancer cell capture and culture. *Biomater Sci. Royal Society of Chemistry;* 2017;5:752–61. [PubMed: 28256649]

58. Ouyang L, Highley CB, Rodell CB, Sun W, Burdick JA. 3D Printing of Shear-Thinning Hyaluronic Acid Hydrogels with Secondary Cross-Linking. *ACS Biomater Sci Eng.* 2016;2:1743–51. [PubMed: 33440472]
59. He Y, Yang F, Zhao H, Gao Q, Xia B, Fu J. Research on the printability of hydrogels in 3D bioprinting. *Sci Rep.* Nature Publishing Group; 2016;1–13.
60. Murphy SV, Atala A. 3D bioprinting of tissues and organs. *Nat Biotechnol.* Nature Publishing Group; 2014;32:773–85. [PubMed: 25093879]
61. Schuurman W, Levett PA, Pot MW, van Weeren PR, Dhert WJA, Hutmacher DW, Melchels FPW, Klein TJ, Malda J. Gelatin-methacrylamide hydrogels as potential biomaterials for fabrication of tissue-engineered cartilage constructs. *Macromol Biosci.* 2013;13:551–61. [PubMed: 23420700]
62. Skardal A, Zhang J, McCoard L, Xu X, Oottamasathien S, Prestwich GD. Photocrosslinkable Hyaluronan-Gelatin Hydrogels for Two-Step Bioprinting. *Tissue Eng Part A.* 2010;16:2675–85. [PubMed: 20387987]
63. Skardal A, Zhang J, Prestwich GD. Bioprinting vessel-like constructs using hyaluronan hydrogels crosslinked with tetrahedral polyethylene glycol tetracrylates. *Biomaterials.* Elsevier Ltd; 2010;31:6173–81. [PubMed: 20546891]
64. Wang LL, Highley CB, Yeh YC, Galarraga JH, Uman S, Burdick JA. Three-dimensional extrusion bioprinting of single- and double-network hydrogels containing dynamic covalent crosslinks. *J Biomed Mater Res - Part A.* 2018;865–75.
65. Suri S, Han L-H, Zhang W, Singh A, Chen S, Schmidt CE. Solid freeform fabrication of designer scaffolds of hyaluronic acid for nerve tissue engineering. *Biomed Microdevices.* 2011;13:983–93. [PubMed: 21773726]
66. Desai V, Shafor C, Spearman BS, Wachs R, Graham J, Atkinson E, Nunamaker E, Schmidt C, Otto KJ, Judy J. Design and Fabrication of a Scalable Tissue-Engineered Electronic Nerve Interface (TEENI). 2016 38th Annu Int Conf IEEE Eng Med Biol Soc.
67. Graham JB, Atkinson EW, Nunamaker EA, Spearman BS, Desai VH, Shafor CS, Natt S, Wachs RA, Schmidt CE, Judy JW, Otto KJ. Histological Evaluation of Chronically Implanted Tissue-Engineered-Electronic-Neural-Interface (TEENI) Devices. 8th Int IEEE/EMBS Conf Neural Eng. 2017;
68. Spearman BS, Desai VH, Mobini S, McDermott MD, Graham JB, Otto KJ, Judy JW, Schmidt CE. Tissue-Engineered Peripheral Nerve Interfaces. *Adv Funct Mater.* 2017;1701713:1–18.

Figure 1: HNMR spectra for MAHA (A) and GMHA (B) synthesized at various molar ratios (5X, 10X, and 20X for both GMHA and MAHA, and 40X for MAHA).

Peaks at 5.6 and 6.1 ppm (a) confirm methacrylation of HA. (C) The relative integration between methacrylate protons at 1.8 (c) and methyl protons present on HA backbone at 1.9 (b) was used to determine degree of methacrylation. The corresponding degrees of methacrylation calculated from NMR are shown in Table 1.

Figure 2: Swelling study results, including swelling ratio, mesh size, and average molecular weight between crosslinks.

A) The swelling ratio represents the ratio between the swelled hydrogel volume and the dry polymer volume. B) The mesh size is the average distance in nm between crosslinks. C) Average molecular weight between crosslinks, as the name indicates, is the polymer molecular weight between crosslinks.

Figure 3: Modulus from indentation of various HA-based hydrogels.

A) Varying concentration with constant methacrylation (16% for GMHA or 30% for MAHA). B) Constant concentration (5 mg/mL) with changing degrees of methacrylation. C) Same data as in B, but plotted as % Methacrylation vs. Modulus. The * indicates $p < 0.05$.

Figure 4: Modulus from indentation on various rat tissues including tibialis anterior (TA) muscle, sciatic nerve, kidney, spleen, heart, liver, brain, spinal cord, and lung. In addition, methacrylated HA was shown to be able to replicate the modulus of lung at the low and to surpass muscle at the high end.

Figure 5: Modulus from indentation on various rat tissues.
Colored regions show the approximate ranges of mechanical properties that are obtainable with the corresponding methacrylated HA (see Table 1).

Figure 6: Modulus from indentation of various multi-component hydrogels, collagen-based hydrogels, and rat sciatic nerve.

Triple-component HA hydrogels were mechanically matched to rat sciatic nerve. The * indicates $p < 0.05$.

Figure 7: % change in cell activity from day 1 to day 3 of Schwann cells.
 Cell activity quantified using alamarBlue assay. Hydrogels without collagen had a decrease in cell activity while all hydrogels with collagen saw a slight increase in cell activity. The * indicates $p < 0.05$, comparisons only done between triple-component and single-component HA hydrogels.

Figure 8: DRG neurite extensions on various hydrogels.

A) Average neurite extension of whole DRGs cultured within hydrogels. GMHA and MAHA hydrogels without additional components. B) Neurite extensions from a DRG cultured in triple-component GMHA. C) Neurite extensions from a DRG cultured in GMHA. To aid visibility, the images of GFP-positive DRGs were inverted. Scale bars = 250 μm. The * indicates $p < 0.05$, comparisons only done between triple-component and single-component HA hydrogels.

Table 1:

Table showing the relationship between stoichiometric ratio of the methacrylate group used for methacrylated HA synthesis (glycidyl methacrylate for GMHA and methacrylic anhydride for MAHA) and the actual degree of methacrylation as determined by HNMR (Figure 1). This also indicates the name used for the GMHA or MAHA used throughout the paper based on the degree of methacrylation.

Hydrogel Type	Hydrogel Name	Ratio of methacrylate group to HA monomer during synthesis	Degree of Methacrylation of HA (%)
GMHA	2.4% GMHA	5X	2.4
	6% GMHA	10X	6
	16% GMHA	20X	16
MAHA	10% MAHA	5X	10
	30% MAHA	10X	30
	50% MAHA	20X	50
	86% MAHA	40X	86